

TOWARDS IMPLEMENTING S3.CURRENT DYNAMICS AND OBSTACLES IN THE LAZIO REGION

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Abstract: The Lazio Region is carrying out a re-industrialization policy following the Europe 2020 targets for economic growth, known as Smart Specialization Strategy (S3). This paper frames industrial policy settings dating back to the second half of the 20th Century in the light of current processes and institutional efforts to set a new season for Industry in Lazio Region. Subsequently, relying upon demographic and socio-economic dynamics over the last two decades, new features in settlement patterns and sector-specific obstacles to sustainable development are addressed with a major focus on the Metropolitan area of Rome (the former Province of Rome). In conclusion, some remarks are drawn mindful of the new globalization wave affecting 'supply chains' of goods and business services from all over the world, of current trends and innovative approaches liable to envisage 'territory' as an opportunity rather than a cost. Difficulties in making different opinions to converge are evident. The proper ground to make it happen should be prepared by a governance able to support place-based inherent 'entrepreneurial discovery processes', while providing negotiating practices framed by general and sectoral policies, and communication approaches to ensure transparency and participation of public at large.

Keywords: Lazio Region, Metropolitan Area, S3, Settlement Patterns, Sustainability Scenarios, Territorial Innovation

1. INTRODUCTION

The Lazio Region accounts for 1.4% of the European GDP and 11.5% of the Italian one. Investments in consumer goods still play a major role (almost 30%), while the production function totals nearly 20% both in terms of capital and new jobs (Crescenzi *et alii*, 2016). Current regional dynamics give rise to differing interpretations.

The first one points out that on-going metropolization processes are shaping new relationships between the Capital City and its wider hinterland, determining a City-Region pattern. Among the 40 Italian municipalities with highest percentage growth between 1991 and 2011, 12 belong to the Province of Rome: Fiumicino, Ardea, Ladispoli, Cerveteri, Anzio, Pomezia, Guidonia Montecelio, Aprilia, Monterotondo, Nettuno, Albano Laziale, Velletri, with an average growth of 25% (Fig. 1). All municipalities fall within a population range deemed scale-efficient (between 30,000 and 80,000 inhabitants), providing good integration level in terms of labor market while avoiding urban congestion (Istituto Nazionale di Urbanistica, 2011).

The second, opposite, interpretation shows evidence about a still prevailing centripetal pattern, tied to the strong appeal of a core area slightly wider than the historic center of Rome: as a matter of fact, 83% of foreign capital invested between 2003 and 2014, and 93% of all new jobs in Lazio, have Rome as their destination (Crescenzi *et alii*, 2016).

The third interpretation investigates current redeployment processes and the rise in higher added value sectors, notably innovative services, currently supported by new regional policies (Smart Specialization Strategies), underlining high-tech manufacturing activities historically present in excellence sub-regional production areas. Whether these emerging arrangements between sub-regional areas are likely to reciprocally exchange goods and people and even enter foreign markets in partial or total autonomy from the lure of Rome is a matter of debate (CER-Unindustria, 2012).

Figure 1: Variation of the resident population in the Lazio Region 2001--2017
Source: Processing of the Authors based on Istat data

On the backdrop of such controversial trend scenarios, this paper intends to address some major issues related to emerging production features and patterns related to the S3 strategy. In the light of new globalization affecting ‘supply chains’ of goods and services from all over the world, does proximity still matter, and, if that is the case, what kind of governance can address both place-specific needs and sector-specific obstacles?

2. DELIBERATE OR UNINTENTIONAL GEOGRAPHIES?

The three industrial revolutions of the past were triggered by technical innovations: the introduction of water and steam-powered mechanical manufacturing at the end of the 18th Century, the division of labor at the beginning of the 20th century and introduction of programmable logic controllers for automation purposes in manufacturing in the 1970s. The upcoming industrial revolution is being triggered by the telematics undermining previous location factors, scattering production processes or incorporating them within urban areas. All these issues, place-based and scale-dependent, are crucial for outlining sustainability paths.

Due to a defective modernization in the 20th Century and to specific industrial patterns, the Lazio Region has somehow been spared from drastic workforce reduction at the end of the 'second revolution'. Conversely, since the early 80s, it has known remarkable diffusion and relocation phenomena, due to production and service activities restructuring - small size businesses have always been the majority -, with no significant consequences in employment rates. Centrifugal trends led SME to accommodate randomly, even though at the initiative of single municipalities industrial estates had been identified within local plans.

Such fragmentation, which proves ineffective both for sector-specific strategies and for the territories, due to general lack in accessibility, high environmental costs, etc., is actually a major concern. The governance system has little influence over these phenomena. It is sufficient to think of soil consumption, notably in the Metropolitan area of Rome (the former Province), which alone touches 71,000 hectares, increasing by 500 hectares between 2012 and 2015 at the expense of agricultural land (Ispra, 2016).

As a matter of fact, the Lazio Region has long been suffering a discrepancy between the 'Ideal region' as it had been envisaged by planners and decision makers, and the 'Real one', resulting both of voluntary and unintentional actions. Top-down and bottom-up processes have been heavily shaping the geographical distribution of assets and facilities. After a phase spurred by the National agency 'Cassa per il Mezzogiorno' concerning location strategies for five major equipped industrial areas (1950s-1980s), the second phase initiated by the Lazio Region since its establishment was far less effective. The new leadership avoided making commitments apart from issuing scant requirements to specialized clusters eligible for subsidies (Regional Law 36/2001). On such occasion, 'districts' and 'local production systems' were identified characterized by different typologies of specialized production (Fig. 2a). These restrictions aiming at targeting incentives in areas with a strictly productive vocation intercept only the 25% of the regional total, corresponding to an occupational capacity of 84,000 employees. As a matter of fact, production homogeneity is not a key feature of the regional industrial structure, which actually presents weak location quotient apart from the pharmaceutical district, the paper and the ceramic one.

Meanwhile, at the initiative of single municipalities, industrial estates have been identified within local plans, generally appealing to small businesses (Fig. 2b).

In turn, provincial planning guidelines accommodating new inter-municipal areas for technopoles and specialized industrial estates have come into force in the 2000s, but they have not been implemented as yet, due to persistent segmentation and lack of communication between programming and implementing at the local level. Moreover, whereas 'Roma Città Metropolitana' has been recently settled by law in the place of the Province of Rome (Law 56/2014), its budget has been shortened by 9/10.

Figure 2: Production systems in Lazio.

2a) Local Production Systems and Districts (Lazio Region, 2001).

2b) Overlap between industrial development consortia identified by the State in the 1950s (Cassa per il Mezzogiorno) and industrial zoning implemented by single municipalities (2006). Credits: Authors' processing from data of Lazio Region.

3. CURRENT DYNAMICS

A research report dating back to 2010 identifies in the Lazio Region 13 'local productive poles' devoted to manufacturing, wholesale trade, hi-tech productions (software, computer services, audiovisual, telecommunications), transport and logistics (Fig. 3, Table 1).

PRODUCTION POLES

1. CIVITA CASTELLANA E VITERBO; 2. RIETI-CITTADUCALE; 3. FIANO ROMANO-FORMELLO; 4. LITORALE NORD (CIVITAVECCHIA-FIUMICINO); 5. BRETELLA NORD (TIVOLI-GUIDONIA); 6. BRETELLA SUD (VALMONTONE-COLLEFERRO); 7. CASTELLI ROMANI; 8. POMEZIA-SANTA PALOMBA; 9. FROSINONE-SORA; 10. LATINA-CISTERNA; 11. CASSINO; 12. SUD PONTINO (FORMIA-GAETA); 13. ROMA

THE DRIVERS OF POLARIZATION

SPONTANEITY (AGRI-FOOD, NAUTICAL)
 EXPANDING METROPOLITAN AREA PROCESS (WHOLESALE, LOGISTICS, AUDIO VISUAL)
 LARGE COMPANIES (MECHANICS, ELECTRONICS, AEROSPACE, PHARMACEUTICALS)
 SYSTEM-BASED ACTIONS (ICT, HI TECH)

Figure 3: Production Poles. Credits: Unioncamere Lazio, Censis (2010).

Table 1. Industrial employment in the Lazio Poles (2010)

EMPLOYMENT BY POLES	PRODUCTION POLES
≈ 85.000	COMUNE DI ROMA
≈ 20.000	POMEZIA-SANTA PALOMBA, LATINA, FROSINONE
≈ 6.000 – 7.000	VITERBO-CIVITA CASTELLANA, CASTELLI, LITORALE NORD, BRETELLA NORD
≈ 3.500 – 4.500	CASSINO, RIETI-CITTADUCALE, BRETELLA SUD, SUD PONTINO
≈ 1.500	FIANO ROMANO-FORMELLO

This survey is highly representative of the regional dynamics, since it intercepts municipalities gathering 87% of the overall population and 92% of total employment and

sets forth trend lines that would not be detectable by the concentration indicators adopted by the Lazio Region for ‘Local Production Systems’ and ‘Districts’ /see Fig. 2).

Overall, these ‘dynamic poles’ total 28.3% of the regional added value closely following financial and real estate brokerage activities (29%) and preceding basic social and health services: public administration, health, education and personal services totaling 25.7%.

Summarizing, four major driving forces are at work selectively affecting industrial sectors: Spontaneity (which is typical to agrifood, nautical and industry); Expansion of the metropolitan area (wholesale, logistic); Bigger players (mechanics, electronics, aerospace, biotechnology and pharmaceuticals); System’s actions (ICT, hi-tech, biotechnology and pharmaceuticals).

In general, the major manufacturing chains unveil lack of specialization, a ‘non-district’ nature and some connections between different production areas which need to be clarified, as it can be inferred in the cases where industrial employment has a larger share.

These productive poles can be considered ‘transversal territorial networks’, ‘multifaceted structures’, often very flexible, mainly due to the substantial presence of craft industries. Their ‘birth’ is not due to imitation or direct filiation of successful businesses in a given sector in a specific location characterized by extensive sub-supply networks, but instead from space arrangements aimed at accommodating diverse and diversified productive settlements. These are usually inter-municipal areas equipped with major facilities: infrastructure, water purification networks, lighting, security, broadband.

It is no coincidence that such ‘hubs’ tend to be managed by a sort of ‘control room’. Sometimes this governance is entrusted to institutional entities, such as consortiums in charge of ‘industrial development areas’ (*Aree di sviluppo industriale*, ASI, deriving from the ‘Cassa per il Mezzogiorno’ experience), while in other cases they are directly managed by the companies operating through independent consortia.

Sometimes, affinities between economic activities are to be sought on the ground of proximity according to the motto of ‘doing different things for the same purpose’, that is enhancing cross-sectoral research and innovation strategies conveying most innovative manufacturing, advanced business services, applied scientific research.

Except for the Civita Castellana ceramic district, coexistence of various manufacturing specialties is the rule. In the Hi-Tech and ICT sectors, the increasing polarization of Formello demonstrates an extension of the sector from the districts of Prati and Saxa Rubra in the Municipality of Rome. As for transport and logistics, the weight of the coast North of Rome from Civitavecchia to Fiumicino is emerging although this sector is also present along the axis connecting Pomezia to Latina, the axis between Monterotondo and Guidonia Montecelio, and in the Frosinone and Ferentino area. Finally, wholesale trade is widespread everywhere around Rome, but the role of the Pontina area South of Rome stands out, thanks to the biggest market of fruit and vegetable in Fondi. The Latina hub proved a major sector in the agro-industry (with numerous companies, especially in Pontinia, Sezze and Priverno), as well as in instrumental mechanics (Latina) and in the nautical sector (especially between Terracina and San Felice Circeo). The pole of Pomezia-Santa Palomba remained leader in the pharmaceutical and biomedical fields: Pomezia alone gathered in 2012 18.5% of all firms present in the region, with significant specialization features both

in chemistry and plastics industry (9.8%) as well as in instrumental mechanics (6.4%). The area of Frosinone confirmed itself as the first regional pole in the field of chemistry and plastics, complemented with a number of other specializations, among which paper industry.

Effective and innovative system-based actions are the result of careful public-private partnerships benefiting the most value-added and high tech industries: hi-tech and ICT, software production and audiovisual productions, or the biotechnology sector. In all these areas, close synergies have been set up between companies, scientific research and public institutions.

Undoubtedly, this interpretation of the productive reality within the Lazio region is the best fitting one. Yet, it is undergoing new challenges. So far, despite the need to fulfill the principles of cooperation and concentration in so-called ‘technopoles’ and ‘parks of activities’ provided by district-scale planning, the sphere of production and that of policy-makers have not been able to streamline innovation processes. The main obstacles are to be found in deep-rooted mistrust from local authorities towards selective solutions; in municipal reluctance towards inter-institutional cooperation (including common agreements); in the absence of incentives for restructuring productive activities, with social, economic and environmental spill-over effects.

4. OLD MATTERS AND NEW CONCERNS

In 2013, ‘Europe 2020’ was set forth in order to support strategic sectors (Common Strategic Framework 2014-2020 and Guidelines for the efficient use of financial resources for the 2014-2020 development). Notably, the S3, acronym for Research and Innovation Smart Specialization Strategy, is conceived to lead the EU towards a more intelligent, sustainable and inclusive economy. The main objectives of this initiative are to help the Member States to: (i) Improve their productivity; (ii) Achieve higher employment rates; (iii) Enhance social cohesion.

In the so-called ‘entrepreneurial discovery process’, a main effort was to be devoted to acknowledge and support local tangible and intangible assets: not only goods, but also relationships, values, knowledge, and the natural and institutional environment liable to give continuity and new perspective to development.

Accordingly, the document ‘Smart Specialization Strategy’ approved by the Regional Council in July 2014 envisages seven macro sectors as the main pivots for forthcoming regional policies: Aerospace; Agri-food; Audiovisual and Creativity; Green Economy; Life Sciences; Cultural Heritage and Technologies for Culture; Safety (Table 2).

As a result, during the General States of Industry (February 2016), 173 projects were presented by hundreds of players, such as large enterprises, SMEs, universities, research centers, associations and local authorities subjects, for a total of 2.3 billion potential investment.

The Lazio Region is committed to invest 100 million Euros for enabling businesses to compete more effectively on the global market; 3 million for redevelopment of brownfield sites; 28 million for Ecologically Equipped Productive Areas (APEA) and related

infrastructure; 30 million for the internationalization; 20 million for supporting the transformation of creative ideas into business ventures.

Apart from deep-rooted sectors settled in specific areas (Aerospace, Life Sciences, and somehow ICT), the other ‘specialization areas’ are seldom physical concentrations featured by high intensity relationships among related enterprises: they are not clusters in the sense of Porter’s definition. Most often, these sectors are dispersed, and as such they need to be better connected. Networks between SMEs, large holdings and multinational companies prove essential both for technology-intensive sectors, such as aerospace, electronics or pharmaceuticals (such sector is the first export sector, accounting for 36% of the regional total), and for others, such as tourism, fashion, design.

Table 2. Features of the S3 Strategy in the Lazio Region

LAZIO DESCRIPTION	CAPABILITIES	TARGET MARKETS	EU PRIORITIES
CREATIVE INDUSTRIES	CREATIVE, CULTURAL ARTS & ENTERTAINMENT LIBRARIES, ARCHIVES, MUSEUMS & OTHER CULTURAL ACTIVITIES	CREATIVE, CULTURAL ARTS & ENTERTAINMENT	CULTURAL & CREATIVE INDUSTRIES
GREEN ECONOMY - SEEN AS A SECTOR IMPORTANT FOR SEVERAL ASPECTS, RANGING FROM TRANSPORT TO ENERGY GENERATION	ENERGY PRODUCTION & DISTRIBUTION		SUSTAINABLE INNOVATION ECO-INNOVATIONS
LIFE SCIENCES	BIOTECHNOLOGY	HUMAN HEALTH & SOCIAL WORK ACTIVITIES HUMAN HEALTH ACTIVITIES (MEDICAL SERVICES)	PUBLIC HEALTH & SECURITY PUBLIC HEALTH & WELL-BEING
AEROSPACE	AIR TRANSPORT & RELATED SERVICES		AERONAUTICS & SPACE AERONAUTICS
SAFETY & SECURITY - UNDERSTOOD IN A VERY BROAD SENSE FROM CITIZENS SECURITY, AGRO-FOOD SECURITY, AIR-TRAFFIC SECURITY, ETC.	PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION, SECURITY & DEFENCE	SERVICES	AERONAUTICS & SPACE SAFETY & SECURITY
AGRI-FOOD: A TRANSVERSAL SECTOR WITH LINKS TO BOTH HIGH-TECH (I.E. BIOTECHNOLOGY) AND LOW-TECH INDUSTRIES (I.E. TOURISM).	AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY & FISHING	FOOD, BEVERAGE & TOBACCO PRODUCTS	
CULTURAL HERITAGE AND TECHNOLOGIES FOR CULTURE	CREATIVE, CULTURAL ARTS & ENTERTAINMENT CREATIVE, ARTS & ENTERTAINMENT ACTIVITIES	INFORMATION & COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES (ICT)	CULTURAL & CREATIVE INDUSTRIES

The Province of Rome is the second largest concentration of population after Milan and, according to the last census, is home to about 7% of the Italian population and 74% of the

population of the Lazio region. It is a highly complex and heterogeneous urban region due to its morphological, functional and settlement characteristics.

Pending the entry into force of *Roma Città Metropolitana*, emerging interrelations between new productive patterns and urban growth account for general restructuring of the regional systems shaping new dependencies and/or autonomization paths from the traditional catchment areas, notably the Capital City and several major production clusters.

The four top ranking traded Regional aggregates of economic activities (*'traded cluster'* according to Porter), belong to so-called 'advanced services' (Table 3). This is consistent with the employment distribution pattern of an advanced, tertiary-led regional economy. In particular, 'Hospitality and Tourism' accounts for a flourishing tourism industry in the Capital City. With respect to manufacturing clusters, 'Biopharmaceuticals' and 'Video and Music' are among the most peculiar economic specializations of the area, the former being led by the presence of big pharmaceutical companies in the province and the latter related to the presence of the most important and productive movie industry nationwide.

Table 3. Roma Provincial Area. Top ranking economic activities

The other Provinces of Lazio (Viterbo-Rieti and Latina-Frosinone) host some of the leading manufacturing clusters in Italy (such as ceramic and paper 'districts'). They also reveal an important presence of biopharmaceuticals (or related) clusters, which are likely to be strongly intertwined with the one identified in the Province of Rome, thus giving further evidence of the pivotal role played by this sector in the area.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Rome and its outer ring keep dominating the regional economy, acting as catalysts for people, enterprises, advanced services and knowledge. This evidence still feeds the assumption that any decrease in production - and average household welfare - can be offset by development activities (among which traditional construction industry) spreading from the center to the outer territories.

On the backdrop, we have to rethink the relationships of interdependence and exchange between different local systems of Lazio (in full autonomy from Rome) and within an increasingly globalized market.

Ultimately, three major trends are likely to affect the forthcoming socio-economic transformations and settlement patterns: (i) Verticalism; (ii) Streamlining; (iii) Atomization.

(i) Ever-changing dynamics within the entrepreneurial milieu between multinational corporations, local businesses and the socio-institutional environment in terms of supply of goods and services requiring intermediate contractors, and/or large enterprises as shareholders of small companies with minority shares. Their overall strategies are differentiating, even within a same sector area, depending on their relationships to local and global contexts.

(ii) Inefficiency in delivering goods and services to the final destination: so-called ‘Last mile’ issue in linking suppliers and customers lays in poor maintenance of the road system and in lack of appropriate investments in infrastructures for interregional connectivity. These criticalities also compel to rethink interdependencies and exchanges within the Region, sometimes in full autonomy from Rome, and under the perspectives of increasingly globalized markets.

(iii) Industry 4.0 is far less polluting, but is all-pervasive. Still, it needs to put down roots in specific living environments with previous settings and rules. Innovation districts worldwide strive to promote models of facilitators - startups, business incubators, consortia - likely to envisage ‘territory’ as an opportunity rather than a cost.

What kind of ‘territorial governance’ can be performed?

When it comes to ‘territory’ and ‘settlement patterns’, we may refer to Local Systems (*Sistemi locali del lavoro*), generated by commuting trips, which have proven a good proxy for daily urban systems, where most activities and interactions among people and economic actors occur independently of any regulations from above. Notwithstanding, they are increasingly regarded as real arrangements which shape daily life.

Or else we may refer to the fundamentals of spatial planning that lie within regional plans, such as the General Plan of the Province of Rome which has come into force in 2008. As a matter of fact, the General Plan aims at reassessing and overhauling the productive structure avoiding and rectifying unfitting settings.

Metropolitan Strategic Parks (PSMs) and Metropolitan Productive Parks (PPMs) are designed to provide good accessibility conditions and the share of facilities among different firms.

In adjunction to existing planning strategies, new regulations are to be established without delay (the Regional Law ‘Testo Unico in materia Urbanistica ed Edilizia’ is under consideration), even more so that new global economies are increasingly run by external factors and exogenous interests, requiring resources and expertise devoted to shaping variable geometries in economic and territorial policies.

Whatever the case, ‘space’ matters.

On the sustainability grounds, the metropolitan area falls short of expectations in several areas: green waste, smart mobility, and especially emerging productive sectors such as the green economy. From the outside, the Roman agglomeration is still perceived as a huge market for goods and services rather than as an employment catchment area or a place to invest money.

In the rest of the Metropolitan area and in the Lazio region, the huge industrial estates dating back to the 50s and 60s are poorly sustainable and far from any idea of “urbanity”: the people working here live elsewhere.

The forthcoming policy Agenda of the Lazio Region should take into due account all these crucial issues, in order to perform a sustainable and resilient approach to ‘territorial innovation’ complying to the strategic objectives of Europe 2020. It is therefore imperative to address the regeneration of these huge hinterlands.

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